

1 **GATA factors are pioneer-type lineage commitment factors in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying (TE) commitment. We describe here discovery of
8 GATA3 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

9 I. GATA activation during trophectoderm commitment.

10 1. We first describe activation of GATA3 during lineage commitment decisions in the embryonic stem
11 cells of the inner cell mass (ICM).

12 2. GATA5 and GATA6 are concomitantly activated during TE commitment in the human embryo.

13 a. Dynamic GATA activation during a developmental transition in sequential fashion is not yet
14 understood

15 3. We next observed activation of the GATA transcription factor *GATA2*.

16 a. *GATA2-AS1*, an antisense RNA produced at the *GATA2* locus, was also activated.
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